

Gender diversity in the historical networks of Soviet film production

Vejune Zemaityte [1], Mila Oiva [2], Ksenia Mukhina [3], Aaron Schecter [4], Noshir S Contractor [5], Maximilian Schich [1]

1: Baltic Film, Media and Arts School, Tallinn University

2: School of Humanities, Tallinn University

3: School of Digital Technologies, Tallinn University

4: Department of Management Information Systems, Terry College of Business, University of Georgia

5: McCormick School of Engineering & Applied Science, the School of Communication and the Kellogg School of Management, Northwestern University

Zemaityte Vejune, Oiva Mila, Mukhina Ksenia, Schecter Aaron, Contractor Noshir S and Schich Maximilian. 2024. "Gender diversity in the historical networks of Soviet film production", *Historical Network Research 2024*, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12598735

Gender inequality prevails in the global film industry. Men dominate most creative jobs in today's film production, as multiple studies have shown (Coles et al. 2022; Elefant et al. 2021; Jones et al. 2024; Verhoeven et al. 2020). However, research on the history of gendered creative labour outside capitalist Western countries is limited. In this paper, we shift our focus to the newsreel production industry of the Soviet Union to examine how gender has historically influenced team formation.

Figure 1. (A) Bipartite director–crew hiring networks of the newsreel production industry in the Soviet Union separated by a decade, coloured by gender (men are green, women are purple, gender unknown are grey), curved edges are drawn clockwise from director to other crew. (B) A stylised example of three newsreel productions as hyperevents e_1 to e_3 occurring at event times $t_1 < t_2 < t_3$ with participating crew members given by uppercase letters A to H, represented as a two-mode actor-event network on the left and as a hypergraph on the right (based on Lerner et al. (2021)).

The Soviet film industry offers an interesting setting for studying the gendered nature of creative labour dynamics. The Soviet doctrine proclaimed gender differences socially irrelevant, and the country had a higher female labour force participation rate across different industry sectors than other nations at the time. During the Soviet era, newsreels, which were short clips shown before films in cinemas, were one of the primary ways of communicating news to the public. The creative networks surrounding the production of newsreels provide a unique case for analysing gendered labour dynamics in film production outside the capitalist context.

We have collected detailed metadata on 1,747 newsreels from the Daily News series produced between 1945 and 1992. This metadata includes information about 1,623 individuals who worked as directors, cinematographers, text editors, and other crew members. The metadata was extracted from the newsreel archive digitised by the Net-Film company. The archive contains more than 9,600 clips from 77 different newsreel series produced by various Soviet film studios.

We examined labour relations through bipartite networks that depict the hiring connections between directors and crew members, with respect to the gender dimension of crew members, as seen in Figure 1A. Using the network approach, we can delve into the relational structures that underlie the historical organisation of creative labour. In the Soviet newsreel production industry, we observed a high prominence of women audiovisual media creators in key leadership roles. This contrasts with the significant gender inequality commonly found in contemporary settings (Elefant et al. 2021; Smith et al. 2019; Verhoeven et al. 2020). Between 1945 and 1992, we found that directorial duties were split almost equally between men and women, and that women directors enjoyed long-lasting careers. Women also appeared to be highly embedded within the production network structures, as evidenced by the high degree centrality of women directors, particularly in the 1960s. Despite this, stark gender inequality persisted in occupational roles of lower prestige, such as that of a cinematographer, where work was mainly dominated by men (90/10%). This aligns with the unequal labour split between the genders in today's film production industries (Coles et al. 2022; Elefant et al. 2021; Jones et al. 2024).

The focus of this submission is the investigation of the role of gender in newsreel team selection using relational hyperevent models (RHEMs; Lerner et al. 2021). The model treats the collaboration of a newsreel team as a hyperevent. In this model, hyperedges represent groups of directors and cinematographers of any size (as depicted in Figure 1B). The model specifies the expected number of newsreels produced by a team of newsreel crew within a given time interval. This is based on several network effects and covariates dependent on actor-level attributes. The underlying data structure of RHEMs is hypergraphs, which are a generalisation of graphs to polyadic, or multi-actor, interaction. The use of RHEMs is justified as collaboration on creative products such as newsreels is inherently polyadic, involving teams of people rather than pairs working together.

We show that women directors form creative teams differently than men, and the gendered hiring behaviour differs based on tenure. Our results indicate that women directors are more likely to hire women camera crews, but this is only observable for directors who are new to the industry. Experienced women directors hire more men onto their teams. However, experienced women directors are the most open to new crews overall, although new women cameras are the most likely to be hired by women directors who are also new.

Our approach combines communication and creative industry perspectives with network science and cultural history. Our study sheds light on the gender dynamics of Soviet Newsreel production and showcases the potential of our methodology for broader comparative research. We can gain further valuable insights by examining other geographic regions, historical periods, and industries with similar group dynamics.

References

- Coles, Amanda, Justine Ferrer, and Vejune Zemaityte. 2022. "A Wider Lens: Australian Camera Workforce Development and Diversity." Australian Cinematographers Society. <https://cinematographer.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/A-Wider-Lens-report-final.pdf>.
- Elefant, Lior, Ety Konor-Attias, Yael Hasson, and Noga Dagan-Buzaglo. 2021. "The Celluloid Ceiling: A Gender-Based Analysis of The Israeli Film Industry." <https://adva.org/celluloid-ceiling/>.

Jones, Pete, Deb Verhoeven, Aresh Dadlani, and Vejune Zemaityte. 2024. "She Must Be Seeing Things! Gender Disparity in Camera Department Networks." *Social Networks* 76 (January): 120–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2023.09.004>.

Lerner, Jürgen, Alessandro Lomi, John Mowbray, Neil Rollings, and Mark Tranmer. 2021. "Dynamic Network Analysis of Contact Diaries." *Social Networks* 66 (July): 224–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2021.04.001>.

Smith, S. L., M. Choueiti, A. Choi, and K. Pieper. 2019. "Inclusion in the Director's Chair: Gender, Race, and Age of Directors across 1,200 Top Films from 2007 to 2018." Annenberg Inclusion Initiative. <http://assets.uscannenberg.org/docs/aii-inclusion-directors-chair-20200102.pdf>.

Verhoeven, Deb, Katarzyna Musial, Stuart Palmer, Sarah Taylor, Shaukat Abidi, Vejune Zemaityte, and Lachlan Simpson. 2020. "Controlling for Openness in the Male-Dominated Collaborative Networks of the Global Film Industry." *PLOS ONE* 15 (6): e0234460. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234460>.